

EPS-Sterna impact assessments

for precipitation nowcasting

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Executive summary

The Arctic Weather Satellite (AWS) was approved at the European Space Agency (ESA) Council meeting at Ministerial level in November 2019 as a new Earth Watch Programme Element. AWS is planned to be launched in 2024, and is seen as a prototype for a future constellation of microwave sounding satellites to support global and regional Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and nowcasting at high latitudes.

EUMETSAT has now started defining such a constellation under the EPS-Sterna Programme. To support the ESA AWS satellite mission and in particular to support the EUMETSAT decision process for EPS-Sterna a number of ESA and EUMETSAT studies have been launched.

The EPS-Sterna mission would be a complement to the existing polar orbiting systems (JPSS and Metop), and will improve the sampling frequency of passive microwave (PMW) data globally and in particular at high latitudes. This can potentially be of value for many applications, but in this study the impact of EPS-Sterna for precipitation nowcasting for Northern Europe is assessed.

A purely data driven model was utilized for this purpose. The model was trained to predict data from a ground based weather radar network for the Baltic Sea Region, using PMW data from sensors of the current weather satellite system, that AWS heritage from. The short range (≤ 4 hours) forecasting performance of the model was evaluated for a summer and a winter period and over an ocean and a mountainous area, and for the time of the day where the current polar orbiting systems provides a good (EPS-Sterna like) data coverage. The prediction performance was found to vary with period and surface type, and best performance was obtained for May, and in particular over ocean, with a rain probability of detection (POD) of 0.75/0.55 and false alarm ratio (FAR) of 0.2/0.3 for the forecast with a lead time of 15/240 minutes. For the December data the performance is significantly lower with a POD of 0.6/0.4 and FAR 0.4/0.5 for the forecast with a lead time of 15/240 minutes. The model was furthermore found to provide a better performance than that of a persistent forecast for all considered performance indicators.

The impact of data from one satellite sensor on the model prediction could then be assessed, and this impact was used as a proxy for what will be gained when data from one sensor are made available to the model. The impact of EPS-Sterna data on the model prediction performance will vary with time of the day, as the coverage of the area considered of the current polar orbiting systems is unevenly distributed during the day, such that the sampling interval is relatively fine during some hours of the day but with large gaps of no data during other periods. The forecasting performance is estimated to increase by about 5 % for the periods of the day where EPS-Sterna provide data relatively close in time to other observations. However, the main performance increase will be obtained when EPS-Sterna "completely" fills in the periods of gap with no data for several hours, since this allows for providing forecasts with significantly smaller lead times. The forecasting performance is estimated to increase by about 20 % if the lead time can be reduced by 120 minutes.

The overall benefit of EPS-Sterna for the data driven precipitation nowcasting approach presented in this study is that it allows for frequent updates of forecasts, with a prediction performance that is close to constant throughout the day, and with a performance increase of about 5 to 20 % for the periods of the day where EPS-Sterna provides data.

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1 Introduction

The Arctic Weather Satellite (AWS) is a new small weather satellite developed by OHB Sweden and the European Space Agency (ESA). The AWS was approved at the European Space Agency (ESA) Council meeting at Ministerial level in November 2019 as a new Earth Watch Programme Element, and is seen as a prototype for a future constellation of microwave sounding satellites to support global and regional Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and nowcasting at high latitudes.

The AWS carries a single instrument, a passive microwave/sub-millimetre sounder, and a single unit of AWS is planned to be launched into a polar orbit in 2024. In addition to this, EUMETSAT is planning for a constellation of several AWS units, called EPS-Sterna. The EPS-Sterna programme is currently being defined by EUMETSAT, in line with the EUMETSAT Destination 2030 strategy to consolidate EUMETSAT's contribution to the realisation of the Vision 2040 of the WMO Integrated Global Observing System. EPS-Sterna is being prepared for a possible candidate extension to the EPS-SG programme in parallel to the EPS-Aeolus (a Doppler wind lidar mission building upon the ESA Aeolus satellite). Both the EPS-Sterna and EPS-Aeolus programmes will be presented to the EUMETSAT Council for decision in 2025. EPS-Sterna shall be seen as an extension and complement to the EUMETSAT and NOAA services delivered by the Joint Polar System (JPS).

To support the ESA AWS satellite mission and in particular to support the EUMETSAT decision process for EPS-Sterna a number of ESA and EUMETSAT studies have been launched, including this one.

If approved by the EUMETSAT member states, EPS-Sterna will considerably improve the global sampling frequency of passive microwave (PMW) data. Together with the existing polar orbiting systems (JPSS and EPS-SG) EPS-Sterna is expected to provide PMW data every 30-60 minutes over Northern Europe.

1.1 Purpose of this document

A fine temporal sampling of PMW data can be of benefit for many applications, but here we focus on assessing the usefulness for precipitation nowcasting and short range forecasting. For this purpose, we have utilized a data driven model for precipitation nowcasting for the Nordic area.

The model is a convolutional and recurrent neural network and is trained to retrieve ground based radar data using PMW data from sensors of the current weather satellite system. The radar data cover the region around the Baltic Sea and are available at a 2 km spatial and 15 minutes temporal resolution. PMW data from the Advanced Technology Microwave Sounder (ATMS) and the combination of Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit-A (AMSU-A) and Microwave Humidity Sounder (MHS) on Metop and NOAA platforms provides about 30 samples/overpasses per day of the considered area, but on a non regular temporal basis, such that the sampling interval is relatively fine during some hours of the day but with considerable gaps of no data during other periods.

The model is trained to retrieve radar reflectivity/precipitation at a 2 km spatial and 15 minutes temporal resolution, and for a lead time of a few hours, and using the available PMW data from the nearest previous hours. The model performance is evaluated for a summer and a winter month, and on top of that, the sensitivity to a fine temporal sampling of PMW data is assessed. The obtained results are then used to estimate the impact of the inclusion of data from an EPS-Sterna constellation on the model prediction performance.

1.2 Structure of this document

Section 2 describes the training data and neural network model applied for the study. This is followed by a description of a number of assessments performed by utilizing the model, and the implications for an EPS-Sterna constellation, in Section 3. Section 4 gives a summary, conclusion, and outlook.

2 Algorithm description

2.1 Training dataset

The training dataset consists of collocated radar data from BALTRAD, a ground based weather radar network for the Baltic Sea Region, and PMW data from polar orbiting satellites covering the year 2020. The radars operate at a frequency of around 5.6 GHz (5 cm wavelength), and have common ranges of 200 - 250 km, with new data being acquired every 5-15 minutes [1]. The BALTRAD composite product used (*pr150^a*) include data from over 40 radar sites and cover the region around the Baltic Sea (see Figure 1) and are available at a 2 km spatial and 15 minutes temporal resolution. PMW data from the following sensors and platforms are used:

- Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit-A (AMSU-A) and Microwave Humidity Sounder (MHS) on Metop-A, Metop-B, Metop-C, NOAA-18, and NOAA-19
- Advanced Technology Microwave Sounder (ATMS, [3]) on NOAA-20 and Suomi-NPP

AMSU-A, MHS, and ATMS are cross-track scanning microwave radiometers for observation of the Earth's atmosphere and surface, and a comprehensive overview of precipitation retrieval from space and PMW data is given in [4] and [5]. AMSU-A has 15 channels operating between 23.8 and 89 GHz, and the samples has a footprint size of 45 km around the nadir view. AMSU-A is designed primarily for measuring atmospheric temperatures. MHS has 5 channels between 90 and 190 GHz and the footprint size is 15 km near the nadir view. MHS is primarily intended for moisture sounding. ATMS, has 22 channels between 23.8 and 190 GHz within a single unit, and with a characteristic that is similar, although not identical, to that of the combination of AMSU-A and MHS. Data associated to temperature sounding channels around 50 GHz, water vapour sounding channels around 183 GHz, and window channels around 89 and 160 GHz are included in the training dataset, and the full set of channels used is described in Table 1. Sterna will include channels that approximately matches the ones used here, and Sterna channels are also described in Table 1. It is noted that Sterna will also include channels operating around 325 GHz, but such data are currently not available from the current polar orbiting sensors.

Training samples are generated for minutes 0, 15, 30, and 45 past the hour for every hour during the day, and the PMW data are mapped to the closest quarter-hour, and re-gridded onto the positions of the BALTRAD grid using bi-linear interpolation. Figure 2 shows at what time during the day we have PMW data covering the centre part of the BALTRAD grid, for all the seven platforms considered in the study, and throughout the entire period used for training the model. It can clearly be seen that the coverage is unevenly distributed during the day, such that the sampling interval is relatively fine during some hours (e.g. between 08:00 and 12:00) of the day but with gaps of no data during other periods (e.g. between 20:30 and 24:00). For the Metop-B, Metop-C and JPSS platforms the ground track and orbital planes are kept stable, but for the other three satellites used in the study there is some drift in local-time ascending node (LTAN) over the year. In particular NOAA-19 has a considerable drift in local overpass times, as seen in the figure, impacting the evolution of the daily time coverage to some extent.

BALTRAD radar reflectivities are used as the training target, but in order to reduce the risk of training the retrieval to reproduce *corrupted measurements* only pixels with a *good* quality are considered. There are numerous error sources that can lead to *corrupted* radar observations, beam blocking and anomalous propagation of the radar beam leading to ground clutter due to atmospheric conditions are some. To determine what qualifies as good quality in this respect we have used the quality index (values between 0 and 1, where 1 is "perfect") dataset available in the composite product used. This quality index is a weight of two components, a static and a dynamic one. The static component is based on areas that are partly hidden by beam blockage, known for each radar site by using a digital elevation model. The dynamic component of the quality estimation is using a pattern recognition model to try detect pixels with reflectivities due to anomalous beam propagation, e.g. ground clutter. We have chosen only pixels with an index greater than 0.8. The exact value to be invoked as threshold here can be debated, but has to balance the need for a large amount of data with sufficient quality. For the limited scope and resources of this project the value of 0.8 was chosen being a qualified estimate taking into consideration a balance between quality and quantity.

Figure 1. The upper row shows BALTRAD composite radar data including associated quality, described in more details in text. The lower row shows topography data from the GTOPO30 dataset, and a definition of regions of interest based on this data (mountainous: elevation > 300 m, ocean: elevation = 0 m).

Figure 2. Time of day (UTC) sampling of the centre position of the BALTRAD grid and for the considered platforms with passive microwave sensors for the year 2020.

a *pn150* is the internal product identity number of the BALTRAD data used. This product includes more than one quantity, but the one used here is the corrected radar reflectivity factor at horizontal polarization (DBZH_CORR). Both an inner (immediately around the radar) and outer filling of data is applied (Pseudo-CAPPI at 500 m), the compositing method is based on selecting the data that are nearest the sea level, and a gauge adjustment technique is applied in order to normalize data from many radars to a common level and to minimize the bias with gauges [2].

Table 1. ATMS, AMSU-A, and MHS channels included in the training dataset, together with a specification of Sterna channels. The channels associated to a given row of the table approximately matches in terms of frequency coverage or in terms of the information content that the channels provide.

ATMS channel	AMSU-A/MHS channel	Sterna channel	Centre Freq. [GHz]	Bandwidth [MHz]	NE Δ T [K]	footprint size [km]
3	AMSU-A 3	11	50.3	180	<0.9	≤ 40 km
4			51.76	180	<0.7	≤ 40 km
5	AMSU-A 4	12	52.8	400	<0.7	≤ 40 km
		13	53.246	300	<0.4	≤ 40 km
6 (DSB ^b)	AMSU-A 5	14	53.596	370	<0.7	≤ 40 km
7	AMSU-A 6	15	54.4	400	<0.7	≤ 40 km
8	AMSU-A 7	16	54.94	400	<0.7	≤ 40 km
9	AMSU-A 8	17	55.5	330	<0.7	≤ 40 km
10	AMSU-A 9	18	57.290344	330	<0.75	≤ 40 km
11	AMSU-A 10		57.290344 \pm 0.217	78	<1.2	≤ 40 km
12	AMSU-A 11		57.290344 \pm 0.3222 \pm 0.048	36	<1.2	≤ 40 km
13	AMSU-A 12		57.290344 \pm 0.3222 \pm 0.022	16	<1.5	≤ 40 km
14	AMSU-A 13		57.290344 \pm 0.3222 \pm 0.010	8	<2.4	≤ 40 km
15	AMSU-A 14		57.290344 \pm 0.3222 \pm 0.0045	3	<3.6	≤ 40 km
16 (88.2 GHz)	AMSU-A 15/MHS 1	21	89	4000	<0.5	≤ 20 km
17	MHS 2 (157 GHz)	31	165.5	2800	<0.6	≤ 10 km
18 (DSB ^b)	MHS 5 (190.311 GHz)	32	176.311	2000	<0.8	≤ 10 km
19 (DSB ^b)		33	178.811	2000	<0.8	≤ 10 km
20 (DSB ^b)	MHS 4 (DSB ^b)	34	180.311	1000	<1	≤ 10 km
21 (DSB ^b)		35	181.511	1000	<1	≤ 10 km
22 (DSB ^b)	MHS 3 (DSB ^b)	36	182.311	500	<1.3	≤ 10 km
		41	325.15 \pm 1.2	2 * 800	<1.7	≤ 10 km
		42	325.15 \pm 2.4	2 * 1200	<1.4	≤ 10 km
		43	325.15 \pm 4.1	2 * 1800	<1.2	≤ 10 km
		44	325.15 \pm 6.6	2 * 2800	<1	≤ 10 km

b This channel operates, as opposed to the associated Sterna channel, in a double sideband (DSB) mode.

Figure 3. The neural network architecture. See text for more details. Figure courtesy of [6].

2.2 Neural network model

The utilized data driven model is a convolutional and recurrent neural network and was originally developed to retrieve or predict radar reflectivity from a combination of data from sensors on polar orbiting and geostationary platforms [6]. This section provides a description of the design of the model but more details are given in [6]. Figure 3 shows the architecture of the neural network, which is composed of four parts:

- **observation branch:** input is the PMW data associated to a time $t = i$, and is responsible to derive information from the spatial pattern of the data using a U-Net convolution structure, originally developed for biomedical image segmentation [7]. The U-Net structure consists of a contracting and an expansive path or encoder and decoder stages. Repeated application of convolutions and max-pooling operations are applied in the contracting path, and the spatial information is reduced while feature information is increased with each encoder stage. The expansive pathway combines the feature and spatial information through a sequence of convolutions and up-sampling (bi-linear interpolation) operations and concatenations with high-resolution features from the contracting path through skip connections (not shown in Figure 3). The output of the observation branch is obtained by projecting the output from each decoder stage onto 16 channels using a simple 1×1 convolution layer,
- **time propagation branch:** input is the hidden state from the previous time step ($t = i - 1$) of the model, otherwise this branch is similar to the observational branch. The model is trained to propagate the hidden state forward in time step of 15 minutes and the model is recurrent in the sense that it uses the hidden state from the previous time step to obtain a retrieval for time $t = i$. This is often referred to as a simple recurrent network or Elman network type,
- **merge block (M):** merges outputs from the observational and time propagation branch, using a separate convolutional block for each scale, in order to obtain the hidden state of the current time step ($t = i$). PMW data are required input to the observational branch for the initial time step and the hidden state provided by the merge block is then only based on the output from the observation branch. For later time steps PMW data are no longer required, and if not given, the hidden state is only based on the output from the time propagation branch,
- **head (H):** a fully-connected head transforms the output to 32 values per pixel, using quantile regression [8] to produce probabilistic estimates of the radar reflectivity, and the quantiles corresponding to quantile fractions $\tau = [0.001, 1/31, 2/31, \dots, 30/31, 0.999]$ are predicted. The reason for using 32 values is here a rather arbitrary choice, and is judged to provide quantiles at a sufficient resolution for the purpose of the study.

It is further noted that no fine-tuning of the model architecture was performed within this study, and the basic configuration applied in [6] is used.

2.3 Training

All the available data described in Section 2.1 for the year 2020 are used as training data. The training is done in two phases, in order to obtain a faster and more stable convergence of the training loss. The model is first trained without including the time propagation branch. Only training samples where both target radar data and PMW data are available are used for this training. The full model is then trained, and to allow for this, the training samples are organized into time-series, e.g. sequences of length 16 separated by 15 minutes time step, where:

- the first entry always contain PMW data,
- the following seven entries may contain PMW data depending on availability,
- the last eight entries, represent the future, and do not include PMW data,
- “ground truth” radar data are available for all time steps.

These sequences of samples were generated with some overlap in terms of time coverage to effectively increase the size of the training dataset. That is, the time associated to the first entry of two sequences may be t_0 and $t_0 + 1h$, and an individual sample can consequently be present in more than one sequence.

For both training phases samples are generated by extracting random crops of $512 * 512$ pixels at 2 km resolution, and using random flip and transpose operations to avoid over-fitting. The AdamW optimizer and a cosine-annealing learning rate schedule with warm restarts every 50th epoch are also applied for both training phases. The training is restarted until the training loss has converged.

One training epoch consists of a forward pass and backward propagation for all samples in the training dataset. The training dataset is on top of the organization described above also organized into batches (one batch may contain one or many sequences of samples) and one training epoch actually consists of iterating over these batches. The batch size (here the number of sequences of samples per batch) can be an important factor for the training of a recurrent network, as using a too low number can in practise result in a failure (vanishing or exploding gradient problem) of the training. However, the required memory needed for the training increases with increasing batch size, and the RAM of the GPUs used for training did not allow for using a batch size greater than two when sequences of 16 samples were used. It was tested to run the training with a batch size of one, but the loss did not converge properly. Consequently, the computational resources used for the training did effectively not allow for training with sequences of greater length than we actually used.

It is noted that the training data are organized in such a way that the state of the model will propagate 15 minutes forward in time each time the model is executed. Furthermore, the model is only trained to make predictions with an effective lead time of 2 - 3 hours (sometimes more than 2 hours since the final entries of the first 8 entries may not contain PMW data), but the model can theoretically be used to make predictions with an associated lead time of arbitrary length. However, if much longer lead times than 4 hours are requested one should also train the model on longer time-series of data than used in this study.

Figure 4. Time of day (UTC) sampling of the centre position of the BALTRAD grid and for the considered platforms with passive microwave sensors for the May and December 2021.

3 Assessments

3.1 Evaluation strategy

The main aim of this study is to assess the impact of an EPS-Sterna constellation for precipitation nowcasting. A full and direct characterisation of the added value of such a constellation is difficult to obtain by utilizing a data-driven model as actual EPS-Sterna data are not available. We here instead aim for estimating the impact of one of the currently operating sensor/platform on the model prediction performance, as this provides information that can be used to assess the benefit of adding data from a sensor/platform. However, prior to this main assessment it is essential that we first verify that the model actually has any skill.

The model performance is evaluated for data covering May and December 2021, and Figure 4 shows the time of day sampling of the centre position of the BALTRAD grid for the considered platforms and for these two periods. Furthermore, the evaluation is separated by surface type, i.e. by ocean and mountainous covered regions as defined by the black and yellow colored areas in the right panel of Figure 1, and in addition to this no data from the outermost 150 pixels (~300 km) were included in the evaluation. We do this to compensate from the fact that weather systems may move into the area, and the model is only fed with data over the area.

The model performance is evaluated by generating 4-hours forecasts with a 15 minutes temporal and 2 km spatial resolution, and “issued” at 12:00 for each day in May and December 2021, and by comparing the predictions to the BALTRAD data. Furthermore, the model is setup to use the available PMW data from the most recent 4 hours in order to make the predictions. All considered platforms provide data covering the BALTRAD region between 08.00 and 12:00 (see Figure 4), and the sampling frequency is thus relatively high during this time compared to other periods of the day. Issuing and evaluating forecasts at this time of day allows for studying the importance of a fine temporal sampling. The impact of a given sensor/platform on the model performance can be assessed, by comparing the model output from two runs, where all available PMW data are used in the reference run, and data associated to the given sensor/platform are rejected in the second run. It was furthermore judged that it was sufficient to limit the evaluation to forecasts with a maximum lead time of 4 hours. This is still greater than the periods with no data coverage (see Figure 4), and the training was anyway only done for a lead time smaller than 4 hours.

Figure 5. Example retrieval for 2021-12-01T12:00Z. The upper row show available PMW data associated to six of the channels used, and for this case the data origins from the SNPP platform. The lower row show the retrieval and the BALTRAD data. The BALTRAD data are unfiltered w.r.t. quality, and retrieved values are only showed for the pixels where BALTRAD data are available, in order to allow for a more simple visual comparison, although the retrieval actually provides data for all pixels of the shown area.

3.1.1 Example retrieval and prediction

The lower panel of Figure 5 shows a qualitative comparison of the radar reflectivity as retrieved by the model and observed (BALTRAD) for 2021-12-01T12:00Z. For reference the upper panel display a selection of ATMS (here onboard Suomi-NPP) channels used by the retrieval. The larger precipitation systems seem to be captured relatively well by the retrieval although the details tend to be a bit more smeared out compared to the BALTRAD data.

This tendency of capturing fewer details is particularly pronounced in the north-eastern part of the scene. Here we are very close to the edge of the ATMS swath where the footprint size is as greatest. On the contrary the horizontal resolution of the PMW input data is better in the south-western part of the scene where also more details can be seen in the retrieved data. However, not all details seen in the BALTRAD data are present even in the south-western part of the scene as the spatial resolution of the PMW data in general is much more coarse than that of the BALTRAD data. Conclusively, Figure 5 shows that the retrieval is more capable of reproducing larger features of the precipitation systems, rather than capturing the fine details.

It should be noted that Figure 5 includes unfiltered BALTRAD data, while both the actual training and evaluation use quality filtered data, as described in Section 2.1. Anyhow, from Figure 5 it is clear that there are some issues with the BALTRAD data. First of all, the coverage of the area is not complete, as part of the radar beam is blocked by orography or even, for some of the radar stations, other obstacles closer to the radar, as e.g. trees. Secondly, the inter-calibration of the radar reflectivity from the various radar stations is not perfect. For example, in the north-easternmost part of the area the radar reflectivity field looks a bit unnatural, with large differences around boundaries of regions covered by different radars. Inter-calibration of radar reflectivity from neighbouring stations is challenging, and one reason for this is that the effective altitude, from which the radar signal is reflected, increases with increasing distance from the radar. Consequently, even though two radar stations may provide data covering the same region, they may not be probing the same volume of air. Thirdly, artifacts in radar data due to erroneous reproduction of reflectivity data, can also be seen in the southwestern part of the area.

Figure 6. Example prediction initiated at 2021-12-01T12:00Z. The upper and lower row show data associated to the evolution of the radar reflectivity of the BALTRAD and predicted data (posterior mean), respectively.

Figure 7. As Figure 6 but for a prediction initiated at 2021-05-17T12:00Z, and also showing data associated to the predicted 0.95 quantile.

Figure 6 and 7 shows a qualitative comparison of the evolution of a 4-hour forecast initiated at 2021-12-01T12:00Z and 2021-05-17T12:00Z, and the BALTRAD data. It is of course impossible to comprehensively evaluate a model from a few forecast occasions only. However, Figure 6 and 7 show that the agreement of the BALTRAD and predicted radar reflectivity in general decreases with increasing lead time, but some aspects of the progression is captured better than others. For example, in Figure 6, the prediction propagates the south-westernmost precipitation system in a north-eastern direction. This is kind of correct for

the easternmost part of the system, but the actual evolution of the complete system is more complex than this according to the BALTRAD data.

The agreement of the BALTRAD and predicted data is quite high around 2021-05-17T12:00Z and for the forecasts with a lead time below 120 minutes (Figure 7). The forecast model propagates the northern part of the precipitation system in a northern direction, and this is also seen in the BALTRAD data. Although the location of the northern part of the system is also relatively well predicted in the forecast with a 120 and 240 minutes lead time, precipitation is clearly underestimated in the easternmost part of the scene. The tendency is that while the precipitation system is propagating forward the extension of the system is decreasing, according to the mean value of the model. However, Figure 7 also displays data associated with the 95th percentile of the prediction, and this data indicates that the precipitation system seems to be increasing in extension, as opposed to the mean data. This is probably related to the fact that the model is uncertain about in which direction the system will propagate. But the 95th percentile forecast provides evidence that the model is "aware" that significantly more precipitation can occur in the eastern part of the area than indicated by the forecast based on the posterior mean, and also in general, that the quantile data provides useful information.

An accurate and optimal forecast model should not only be able to predict how existing precipitation systems propagate forward in time, but it must also be able to realistically capture conditions favourable for and predict the initiation of precipitation. It is unclear whether or not the model is actually able to capture such precipitation formation events. But as the model is fed with time series of PMW data, containing information about vertical structures of atmospheric temperature and moisture, we believe this should allow for the model to learn for what type of cloud free and cloudy atmospheres that precipitation can occur, at least to some extent. However, this has not been investigated further as this was out of scope for the current study, and furthermore it is likely that more training data than actually used for the current study are needed for this purpose.

It is possible that the model has a limited ability to predict precipitation formation events, and that it is mainly capable of predicting the evolution of already existing cloud and precipitation systems. It is also possible that the model will tend to propagate the systems forward in a rather simplistic manner, i.e. move a system along a single direction based on the observed displacement of the most recently used PMW data. Though such a prediction will probably be a fairly good one in many cases it also has to be acknowledged that the PMW data associated to a given time do not necessarily cover the complete area, and hence the quality of the prediction may vary across the area depending on the data coverage of the used PMW data.

3.1.2 Metrics

The following metrics are used for evaluating the model:

- root mean square error (RMSE) or difference between predicted and actual reflectivity,
- correlation between predicted and actual reflectivity,
- probability of detection (POD) and false alarm rate (FAR) scores that are computed based on a prescribed threshold value of radar reflectivity,
- critical success criteria (CSI) is a verification measure of the categorical forecast performance and here calculated as $CSI = 1 / (1 / (1 - FAR) + 1 / POD - 1)$.

Hence, the model is evaluated based on how well it can predict radar reflectivity. Radar reflectivity is closely connected to the actual precipitation rate, that is probably more relevant for most applications, and Table 2 provides an approximate relationship between radar reflectivity and precipitation rate. It is noted that precipitation is commonly referred to as drizzle or rain if the precipitation rate is below or above 0.5 mm/hour (radar reflectivity around 15 dBZ), respectively. The model's ability to detect rain is mainly evaluated using a radar reflectivity threshold value of 15 dBZ, as described in more details later in this section.

Table 2. Radar reflectivity and approximate rain and snow fall rate [9].

Radar reflectivity [dBZ]	Rain rate [mm/hour]	Snow rate [mm/hour]
-10	0.0063	0.015
0	0.029	0.05
10	0.14	0.16
20	0.63	0.5
30	2.9	1.6
40	14	5
50	63	16

Figure 8. Probability density function of the actual radar data, and for four types of output from the model for the 15 minutes forecast and over ocean and for May 2021. See text for more details.

Figure 9. As Figure 8 but showing the probability distribution.

The model provides a probabilistic estimate of radar reflectivity or data corresponding to 32 quantile fractions or percentiles for each pixel, and the remaining part of this section describes how the quantile data are used to obtain the metrics described above. The quantile data provides a discrete representation of the posterior reflectivity probability distribution or $P(\text{dBZ} \leq X)$, and from the quantile data we can also obtain the probability density function (PDF). It is often convenient to report or use a single value for a given pixel and the most natural options are to use the mean value, the median value, or the most likely value, where the mean value is obtained by integrating the data associated to all quantile fractions over the PDF, and the median value corresponds to the data associated to the 0.5 quantile or 50th percentile. For rain detection one can also consider to use data associated to some other quantile than the 0.5 quantile.

Figure 8 and 9 show PDFs or occurrence frequencies and distributions, respectively, of the actual radar data and four types of output from the model associated to the 15 minutes forecast and for all pixels associated to ocean and for May 2021. First of all it can be noted from Figure 9 that only a small fraction of all pixels (~7 %) have an actual reflectivity above 15 dBZ (rain). It is also noted (from Figure 8) that the 50th percentile data contains relatively more high reflectivity values and less low reflectivity values than the posterior mean data. The posterior mean values never exceeds ~23 dBZ, and the associated PDF differ significantly from the actual PDF, and consequently the posterior mean data are not useful for detecting anything but light precipitation. The various PDFs of the model output deviates significantly from each other, indicating that the retrieval uncertainty is quite high.

Instead of using data associated to a particular percentile it is also possible to pick a random value from the posterior probability distribution, here referred to as the *sampled* dataset. From Figure 8 we can see that the agreement of the *sampled* and actual distribution is fairly high, indicating that the model provides a probabilistic estimate that in a statistical sense is consistent to the observed data. However, a naive random realization generates a noisy forecast in the spatial domain so it is not really useful to use such data for further processing. From Figure 9 we can also see that the actual distribution of radar reflectivity lies somewhere between that of the 50th and 90th percentile data. Figure 10 shows the model performance in terms of POD and FAR for various threshold values of radar reflectivity and for various outputs from the model for the 15 minutes forecast and over ocean and for May 2021. Figure 10 shows for example that the POD score is relatively high if the 90th percentile data is used for detection, but on the other hand the FAR is also relatively high. Furthermore, the 50th percentile and posterior mean data give a relatively low FAR, but also a relatively low POD. The 70th percentile data give an intermediate performance both in terms of POD and FAR and are therefore, hereinafter, used for the further model evaluation based on the categorical statistical POD and FAR metrics.

Figure 11 shows model performance in terms of POD, FAR, and CSI as function of lead time and for ocean and May 2021, and for various radar reflectivity threshold values, and using the 70th percentile data for detection. The POD and FAR decreases and increases with increasing lead time as expected, but the performance is in general better than that of a persistent forecast, indicating that the model has some skill. It can be noted that the POD and FAR varies somewhat with dBZ threshold value. The tendency is that POD and FAR is decreasing with increasing radar reflectivity threshold value for the forecasts with longer lead times. Evaluating the model performance for POD and FAR and using radar reflectivity threshold value above 20 dBZ is difficult due to the fact that the actual occurrence frequency is low and the limited size of evaluation dataset gives a noisy result. For the remaining part of the evaluation we will use a threshold value of 15 dBZ, but it is noted that using another threshold value gives a slightly different result.

Figure 10. Model performance in terms of POD vs. FAR for five types of output from the model for the 15 minutes forecast and over ocean and for May 2021. Data are shown for five threshold values of radar reflectivity (0, 5, 10, 15, 20 dBZ) and the size of the marker is coded such that the size is increasing with increasing threshold value.

Figure 11. Model performance in terms of POD, FAR, and CSI as function of lead time and for ocean and May 2021, and for various radar reflectivity threshold values as indicated in the legend and using the 70th percentile data for detection. The performance of a persistent forecast (the 15 minutes forecast) is shown in dashed lines.

Figure 12. Model performance as function of lead time over ocean and mountainous region for 4-h forecasts issued at 12:00 for each day in May and December 2021. The performance of a persistent forecast (the 15 minutes forecast) is shown in dashed lines.

3.2 Performance by period and surface type

Figure 12 shows the model performance over the ocean and mountainous region and for May and December 2021. In general, the RMSE and FAR increases and correlation and POD decreases as function of lead time and as expected by a prediction model. The overall best performance is obtained for data covering May, and in particular for the ocean area. One reason for this is probably related to the fact that snowfall is a more common precipitation type for December than May, and snowfall retrieval is more challenging than rainfall retrieval from space as the snowfall impact on the observation is easily obscured by other contributions as e.g. discussed [4]. Anyhow, the model performs better than a persistent forecast for both of the periods and the surface types and for all performance indicators. For example, the correlation is about 15% greater for the forecast with a lead time of 120 minutes compared to the persistent forecast, indicating that the model has some type of skill. Although it might not be very impressive for a model to outperform a persistent forecast it is important to verify that this is actually the case, since otherwise it is not justifiable to use the model for further assessments.

Figure 13. Model performance over ocean and for 4-h forecasts issued at 12:00 for each day in May 2021, and for five forecast types; a reference one where all available data are used, and four other ones where data from one of the sensor were excluded for each one of them. Also shown is the performance for a persistent forecast for each of the forecast type as another reference.

3.3 Impact of one of the sensor/platform on the model prediction performance

We here attempt to assess the model performance sensitivity to a fine temporal sampling of PMW data. Figure 13 shows estimated model performance data for a number of different forecast runs and for the ocean area and May 2021 data. Figure 13 includes data associated to a reference run where all available PMW data were consumed in order to make the predictions, and also data from four other runs where data associated to one of the platform were excluded as input to the model for each one of them. From Figure 12 we can see that the performance clearly drops, i.e. RMSE and FAR increases and correlation and POD decreases w.r.t. the reference run, for the forecasts where no data associated to the SNPP and NOAA-20 platforms are used, whereas this is not the case for the runs where data from one of the Metop platform are excluded. One basic reason for this is that data from NOAA-20 and SNPP are in general available closer to 12:00 than for the two Metops, as can be seen from Figure 4, and it thus seems that little or no weight is given to data from the Metops for forecast issued at 12:00. However, a clear performance loss is obtained for the forecasts with a lead time of 15 - 120 minutes when NOAA-20 or SNPP data are excluded, but the loss is less prominent for forecast with longer lead times, probably explained by the fact that the model performance in general decreases with increasing lead time.

Figure 14 and 15 show similar data as shown in Figure 13 but now also including data for the mountainous region and December 2021. The sensitivity is fairly consistent for both the periods and surface types. No significant performance loss is obtained when data associated to the Metop platforms are excluded, whereas a decrease in the order of 5% is obtained for the performance indicators used and for forecast with a 15 and 60 minutes lead time, when filtering out NOAA-20 and SNPP data. A bit larger spread is found in the results for the forecast with a 240 minutes lead time.

Figure 14. Impact of one of the sensor/platform on the model prediction performance for forecasts with lead time of 15, 60, and 240 minutes "issued" at 12:00 for May and December 2021, and for ocean and mountainous region.

Figure 15. As Figure 14 but showing the difference compared to the reference forecast.

Figure 16. Impact of an amplified inter-platform bias on the model performance for 4-h forecasts issued at 12:00 for each day in May 2021, and for the ocean area. Data are shown for a reference run using all available data and for a modified run where a simple temperature bias of 2 K was added for all channels associated to NOAA-20/ATMS data.

3.3.1 Model sensitivity to inter-platform channel bias

In the preceding section it was shown that the model performance is sensitive to the presence of ATMS data for the forecast issued around 12:00. In particular, neglecting ATMS data onboard NOAA-20 in the model input have a clear negative impact on the model performance. We here introduce a simple temperature bias of 2 K for all channels associated to NOAA-20/ATMS, in order to assess the sensitivity to an inter-platform bias for the model performance. In the context of EPS-Sterna we think it is relevant to assess such an inter-platform channel bias. It is expected that it may be more challenging to maintain stability in channel performance, in terms of bias and $Ne\Delta T$, across platforms for small satellites, compared to the larger platforms in the backbone missions (JPSS and Metop).

Figure 16 shows a comparison of the forecast performance for a reference run and for a forecast run where such a speculative 2 K bias is added to the NOAA-20/ATMS data. The bias impact on the performance is marginal, and this can be explained by the fact that the model extracts information from the pattern or features of the observed data, rather than from the absolute values. Consequently, the model performance is not very sensitive to a simple bias like the one tested here.

Figure 17. Estimated time of day (UTC) sampling of the centre position of the BALTRAD grid (see Figure 1), for the current sensors and the nominal EPS-Sterna constellation.

3.3.2 Implications for an EPS-Sterna constellation

The results from the preceding sections indicates that a fine temporal sampling of PMW data is valuable for a precipitation nowcasting and short range forecasting model, and consequently the inclusion of data from an EPS-Sterna constellation into the model will lead to an improved prediction performance. The nominal EPS-Sterna constellation, OP3-6SAT, includes in total 6 satellite, or 2 satellites in 3 orbital planes, and a degraded scenario, OP3-3SAT, that we also refer to in this section, includes in total 3 satellite, or 1 satellite in 3 orbital planes.

Figure 17 shows an estimate of how the PMW data sampling of the BALTRAD grid would look like when data from the nominal EPS-Sterna constellation are included, and Figure 18 report the data as an *average time to coverage* metric. From Figure 17 and 18 we can see that such a constellation will, to a large extent, fill in the periods of gap with a sparse data sampling data, and the resulting maximum *time to coverage* metric will be reduced by up to a factor of three, allowing for making forecast with a greatly reduced effective lead time.

The main benefit of an EPS-Sterna constellation for precipitation nowcasting should be that the periods of gaps with no data in the current system are filled in. For example, a forecast prediction issued at 23:00 and using data only from the present observation system can only rely on data that has an age of more than 120 minutes, and consequently the effective lead time of the forecasts will be at least 120 minutes, and by looking at e.g. Figure 12 we can see a clear drop in performance when the lead time is increased by 120 minutes. The greatest performance drop is obtained for the forecasts with very short lead time, e.g. the CSI drops from about 0.65 to 0.5 (more than a 20 % drop) for the 15 and 135 minutes forecast, but the performance also decreases significantly for lead times between 120 and 240 minutes (CSI decreases from 0.5 to below 0.45).

Figure 18. Average time to coverage - as a metric for time coverage over the day for the data and area displayed in Figure 16.

The two satellites in each orbital plane of the nominal ESP-Sterna constellation will provide a data sampling that reminds about what is obtained for the combination of SNNP and NOAA-20 platforms but for a different period of the day. The impact on the model performance by using data from only one of the platforms was studied in the preceding section, and it was found that the performance drops by about 5% in this case. This implies that the nominal constellation outperforms the degraded scenario that only includes 1 satellite in each orbital plane by about 5 % in terms of model performance. It is intuitively easy to understand that the nominal constellation outperforms the degraded scenario as the nominal constellation allows for making forecasts with a shorter effective lead time for 50% of the period covered by the two satellites.

Thus, the addition of data from the nominal EPS-Sterna constellation to the utilized model is anticipated to provide a forecasting performance that is close to homogeneous for all hours of the day, and by filling in periods of gap with no data coverage of the present observation system the forecasting performance is estimated to increase by 5 to 20 % depending on time of the day and the forecast lead time.

4 Summary, conclusions, and outlook

A data driven model for precipitation nowcasting and short range forecasting for the BALTRAD domain was utilized, in order to assess the benefit of using additional data from an EPS-Sterna constellation. The model is trained to predict ground based radar data from PMW data associated to sensors of the current EUMETSAT and NOAA polar satellite system. The model was evaluated for two distinctly different periods (May and December 2021), and both for an ocean and mountainous area. The prediction performance was found to vary with period and surface type, and best performance was obtained for May, and in particular for the ocean, with a rain POD of 0.75/0.55 and FAR of 0.2/0.3 for the forecast with a lead time of 15/240 minutes. For the December data the performance is significantly lower with a POD of 0.6/0.4 and FAR 0.4/0.5 for the forecast with a lead time of 15/240 minutes. The model was furthermore found to provide a better performance than that of a persistent forecast in terms of RMSE, correlation, POD, and FAR. For example, the correlation is about 15% greater for the forecast with a lead time of 120 minutes compared to the persistent forecast, and therefore the model was judged to be useful to apply for further assessments.

The inclusion of data from an EPS-Sterna constellation into the model is anticipated to lead to an improved prediction performance. This is most easily explained by the fact that by including such data the effective lead time of the forecasts can be reduced. The model performance sensitivity to a fine temporal sampling of PMW data was assessed, for forecasts with a lead time up to 4 hours and "issued" at 12:00 for each day of the two test periods, in order to allow to indirectly assess the benefit of both a nominal and degraded EPS-Sterna constellation for precipitation nowcasting. Be aware that we did not study the effects of noise level in the data which, on the other hand, may have an impact on the model performance.

Around this time of the day the sensors of the existing polar orbiting system provide a relatively fine sampling compared to some other periods of the day. A performance decrease of about 5 % in RMSE, correlation, and CSI is obtained for the forecasts with a 15 - 60 minutes lead time when data associated to the NOAA-20 or SNPP are excluded from the forecast generation. NOAA-20 and SNPP follows the same orbital plane and are separated by 50 minutes, and provides data closer to 12:00 than the Metops. No significant performance loss was observed when data were filtered out for sensors that provides data earlier than this, and thus the model mainly gives weight to the most recent data. This implies that the nominal constellation would outperform the degraded scenario by about 5 % in terms of model performance, for the periods of the day when EPS-Sterna provide data. In addition to this, it was found that the model performance is only marginally sensitive to an inter-platform brightness temperature bias, and consequently, it is not crucial for an EPS-Sterna constellation to provide accurately calibrated data for machine learning nowcasting applications.

However, the main benefit of an EPS-Sterna constellation will be obtained around the periods of the day where the current observation system does not provide any fresh data for two hours or more. Around these times of the day the short range forecast performance can be increased by up to 20% by using data from such a constellation.

Nevertheless, it should clearly be pointed out that the exact values of all numbers presented here must be treated with some care. First of all, the model used in this assessment is a rather complex and newly developed model and has only been applied within quite limited studies, and we can not rule out that it might be possible to obtain a much better model prediction performance, e.g. by tuning of the model architecture/parameters. Secondly, one year of training data was used for the training of the model, and this is probably on the low side, in particular for heavy precipitation events that are quite rare over the considered domain. Thirdly, Sterna/AWS will also include four channels operating around 325 GHz and data from these channels can potentially be useful for the precipitation nowcasting, but no such data were considered in the present study. Fourthly, the Sterna/AWS sounder will have better horizontal resolution compared to AMSU/MHS and better or comparable to MWS/ATMS, which should allow it to obtain more detailed information of precipitation signatures. Fifthly, the model can probably learn the underlying physics better if the training data include better temporal resolved time-series as will be possible if actual EPS-Sterna data are used. Sixthly, the model was here restricted to only make use of PMW data, and the prediction performance can potentially increase if other data types are included, e.g. NWP data or data from geostationary platforms.

5 References

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